

APPENDIX I FOR THE DOSSIER: A HYPOTHESIS FOR THE ELABORATION OF HEPTATONIC SCALES

COMPLETE DATABASE OF THE QUARTER-TONE GENERATIONS FOR NI=7 (HEPTATONIC SCALES) WITH THE LIMITED ALPHABET '2, 3, 4, 5, 6'

This appendix is not included in the printed version of NEMO-Online Vol. 4. The database is complete for the alphabet '2, 3, 4, 5, 6' quarter-tone intervals.

Other remarks:

- Smallest interval in use: 2 quarter-tones
- Largest interval in use: 6 quarter-tones
- NI=7 intervals
- H. → hyper-system
- Value → value of the intervals composing the sub-system
- NS → Number of systems in the hyper-system
- NSS → Number of sub-systems in the hyper-system
- 5ths → Number of sub-systems with a direct fifth (beginning with the first interval)
- 4ths → Number of sub-systems with a direct fourth (beginning with the first interval)
- FF → Number of sub-systems with a direct fifth AND direct fourth (beginning with the first interval)
- Sub-systems are classified under their systems then hyper-systems:
 - sys. → Number of systems
 - 5ths, 4ths, FF → Same as above, but in the system
 - filter 'Min' works for suits of two conjunct semi-tones, whenever filter 'Umin' starts at three; M347 tests for two conjunct semi-tones in positions '3', '4', and '7'
 - First line in each system describes it; for example, in the first system in the set (hyper-system 1, system 1 under the heading "Sub-systems" in the appendix) the line describing the system is:
 - (0; 1; 1; 2 2 2 2 4 6 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes
 - the first "0" characterizes the database (here octavial),
 - the first "1" gives the rank of the hyper-system,
 - the second "1" gives the rank of the system within the hyper-system,
 - the following seven digits after the comma give the values of the successive intervals in the sub-system, with "5th" and "4th" giving the total numbers, respectively (but equal in the octavial case) of sub-systems with direct fifth then fourth within the system, while FF gives the number of sub-systems with direct fourth AND fifth.
 - For the following seven rows describing the successive sub-systems in the system, the indications are self-explicit, except for the first two digits, either "00", "10" or "11": "00" stands for "unknown in the traditional repertoire of *maqām* music", "10" for "found in the specialized literature but its traditional use is not confirmed", and "11" for "scale of a traditional *maqām* – confirmed".

These criteria were established for the 2003 Ph.D. thesis of the author: further research shows that many scales could (should) be reintegrated in the "traditional" ones ("11"), a task that will require, however, more time and research.

I. HYPER-SYSTEMS

Hyper-system	Value	NS	NSS	5ths
Hyper-system No. 1	2 2 2 2 4 6 6	15	105	58
Hyper-system No. 2	2 2 2 2 5 5 6	15	105	23
Hyper-system No. 3	2 2 2 3 3 6 6	30	210	54
Hyper-system No. 4	2 2 2 3 4 5 6	120	840	208
Hyper-system No. 5	2 2 2 3 5 5 5	20	140	56
Hyper-system No. 6	2 2 2 4 4 4 6	20	140	80
Hyper-system No. 7	2 2 2 4 4 5 5	30	210	40
Hyper-system No. 8	2 2 3 3 3 5 6	60	420	120
Hyper-system No. 9	2 2 3 3 4 4 6	90	630	168
Hyper-system No.10	2 2 3 3 4 5 5	90	630	210
Hyper-system No.11	2 2 3 4 4 4 5	60	420	96
Hyper-system No.12	2 2 4 4 4 4 4	3	21	12
Hyper-system No.13	2 3 3 3 3 4 6	30	210	46
Hyper-system No.14	2 3 3 3 3 5 5	15	105	29
Hyper-system No.15	2 3 3 3 4 4 5	60	420	120
Hyper-system No.16	2 3 3 4 4 4 4	15	105	30
Hyper-system No.17	3 3 3 3 3 3 6	1	7	0
Hyper-system No.18	3 3 3 3 3 4 5	6	42	12
Hyper-system No.19	3 3 3 3 4 4 4	5	35	18

II. SYSTEMS

H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF														
3	27	2326236	1	1	0	4	59	2246325	2	2	1								
3	28	2326263	2	2	0	4	60	2246523	2	2	1								
1	1	2222466	3	3	1	3	29	2326326	1	1	0	4	61	2252346	3	3	2		
1	2	2222646	4	4	3	3	30	2332626	3	3	0	4	62	2252364	2	2	1		
1	3	2222664	3	3	1							4	63	2252436	1	1	0		
1	4	2224266	3	3	0							4	64	2252463	1	1	0		
1	5	2224626	4	4	1	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	4	65	2252634	0	0	0		
1	6	2226246	4	4	2							4	66	2252643	1	1	0		
1	7	2226264	4	4	1	4	1	2223456	1	1	0	4	67	2253246	4	4	2		
1	8	2226426	4	4	2	4	2	2223465	1	1	0	4	68	2253264	3	3	1		
1	9	2226624	3	3	0	4	3	2223546	3	3	2	4	69	2253426	3	3	1		
1	10	2242266	4	4	1	4	4	2223564	3	3	1	4	70	2253624	2	2	0		
1	11	2242626	4	4	1	4	5	2223645	1	1	0	4	71	2254236	1	1	0		
1	12	2246226	5	5	3	4	6	2223654	1	1	0	4	72	2254263	0	0	0		
1	13	2262264	5	5	3	4	7	2224356	2	2	0	4	73	2254326	2	2	0		
1	14	2262426	4	4	1	4	8	2224365	1	1	0	4	74	2254623	1	1	0		
1	15	2262624	4	4	1	4	9	2224536	2	2	0	4	75	2256234	0	0	0		
						4	10	2224563	1	1	0	4	76	2256243	0	0	0		
						4	11	2224635	3	3	1	4	77	2256324	1	1	0		
						4	12	2224653	3	3	1	4	78	2256423	1	1	0		
H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	4	13	2225346	3	3	2	4	79	2262345	2	2	0		
2	1	2222556	2	2	1	4	14	2225364	3	3	1	4	80	2262354	3	3	1		
2	2	2222565	0	0	0	4	15	2225436	1	1	0	4	81	2262435	3	3	1		
2	3	2222655	2	2	1	4	16	2225463	1	1	0	4	82	2262453	3	3	1		
2	4	2225256	1	1	0	4	17	2225634	1	1	0	4	83	2262534	3	3	1		
2	5	2225265	0	0	0	4	18	2225643	1	1	0	4	84	2262543	2	2	0		
2	6	2225526	3	3	1	4	19	2226345	1	1	0	4	85	2263245	1	1	0		
2	7	2225625	0	0	0	4	20	2226354	2	2	0	4	86	2263254	2	2	1		
2	8	2226255	3	3	1	4	21	2226435	3	3	2	4	87	2263425	1	1	0		
2	9	2226525	1	1	0	4	22	2226453	3	3	2	4	88	2263524	3	3	1		
2	10	2252256	1	1	0	4	23	2226534	2	2	0	4	89	2264235	4	4	2		
2	11	2252265	1	1	0	4	24	2226543	1	1	0	4	90	2264253	4	4	2		
2	12	2252526	2	2	0	4	25	2232456	1	1	0	4	91	2264325	3	3	2		
2	13	2252625	1	1	0	4	26	2232465	1	1	0	4	92	2264523	3	3	2		
2	14	2255226	4	4	2	4	27	2232546	3	3	2	4	93	2265234	2	2	1		
2	15	2262525	2	2	0	4	28	2232564	2	2	1	4	94	2265243	1	1	0		
						4	29	2232645	1	1	0	4	95	2265324	3	3	1		
						4	30	2232654	0	0	0	4	96	2265423	1	1	0		
H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	4	31	2234256	1	1	0	4	97	2324256	0	0	0		
3	1	2223366	2	2	0	4	32	2234265	0	0	0	4	98	2324265	1	1	0		
3	2	2223636	1	1	0	4	33	2234526	2	2	0	4	99	2324526	1	1	0		
3	3	2223663	0	0	0	4	34	2234625	1	1	0	4	100	2324625	2	2	0		
3	4	2226336	2	2	0	4	35	2235246	4	4	2	4	101	2325246	2	2	0		
3	5	2226363	1	1	0	4	36	2235264	3	3	1	4	102	2325264	2	2	0		
3	6	2226633	2	2	0	4	37	2235426	3	3	1	4	103	2325426	2	2	1		
3	7	2232366	2	2	0	4	38	2235624	2	2	0	4	104	2325624	1	1	0		
3	8	2232636	1	1	0	4	39	2236245	0	0	0	4	105	2326245	2	2	1		
3	9	2232663	1	1	0	4	40	2236254	0	0	0	4	106	2326254	1	1	0		
3	10	2233266	3	3	0	4	41	2236425	1	1	0	4	107	2326425	2	2	0		
3	11	2233626	3	3	0	4	42	2236524	1	1	0	4	108	2326524	0	0	0		
3	12	2236236	1	1	0	4	43	2242356	3	3	1	4	109	2342526	1	1	0		
3	13	2236263	1	1	0	4	44	2242365	1	1	0	4	110	2342625	2	2	1		
3	14	2236326	2	2	0	4	45	2242536	3	3	1	4	111	2352426	3	3	1		
3	15	2236623	1	1	0	4	46	2242563	1	1	0	4	112	2352624	3	3	1		
3	16	2262336	3	3	0	4	47	2242635	2	2	0	4	113	2362425	1	1	0		
3	17	2262363	2	2	0	4	48	2242653	2	2	0	4	114	2362524	0	0	0		
3	18	2262633	3	3	0	4	49	2243256	2	2	1	4	115	2425263	0	0	0		
3	19	2263236	2	2	0	4	50	2243265	0	0	0	4	116	2425326	3	3	1		
3	20	2263263	1	1	0	4	51	2243526	3	3	1	4	117	2426253	3	3	1		
3	21	2263326	3	3	0	4	52	2243625	0	0	0	4	118	2426325	1	1	0		
3	22	2263623	1	1	0	4	53	2245236	2	2	1	4	119	2432526	2	2	1		
3	23	2266233	3	3	0	4	54	2245263	0	0	0	4	120	2432625	1	1	0		
3	24	2266323	2	2	0	4	55	2245326	3	3	1								
3	25	2323266	2	2	0	4	56	2245623	0	0	0								
3	26	2323626	2	2	0	4	57	2246235	3	3	1								
						4	58	2246253	3	3	1								

Amine Beyhom

A Hypothesis for Heptatonic Scales

9	57	2342643	1	1	0	10	31	2323455	3	3	1	11	5	2243445	0	0	0
9	58	2343246	2	2	0	10	32	2323545	3	3	1	11	6	2243454	0	0	0
9	59	2343264	2	2	0	10	33	2323554	3	3	1	11	7	2243544	1	1	0
9	60	2343426	2	2	1	10	34	2324355	2	2	0	11	8	2244345	1	1	0
9	61	2343624	1	1	0	10	35	2324535	2	2	0	11	9	2244354	1	1	0
9	62	2344236	1	1	0	10	36	2324553	3	3	1	11	10	2244435	2	2	1
9	63	2344263	1	1	0	10	37	2325345	3	3	1	11	11	2244453	2	2	1
9	64	2344326	1	1	0	10	38	2325354	2	2	0	11	12	2244534	1	1	0
9	65	2346243	1	1	0	10	39	2325435	3	3	1	11	13	2244543	1	1	0
9	66	2346324	1	1	0	10	40	2325453	3	3	1	11	14	2245344	1	1	0
9	67	2362434	0	0	0	10	41	2325534	2	2	0	11	15	2245434	0	0	0
9	68	2362443	1	1	0	10	42	2325543	3	3	1	11	16	2245443	0	0	0
9	69	2363244	2	2	0	10	43	2332455	3	3	1	11	17	2253444	2	2	1
9	70	2363424	1	1	0	10	44	2332545	3	3	1	11	18	2254344	1	1	0
9	71	2364243	2	2	0	10	45	2332554	3	3	1	11	19	2254434	0	0	0
9	72	2364324	1	1	0	10	46	2334255	3	3	0	11	20	2254443	0	0	0
9	73	2424336	2	2	0	10	47	2334525	2	2	0	11	21	2324445	2	2	1
9	74	2424363	1	1	0	10	48	2335245	2	2	1	11	22	2324454	1	1	0
9	75	2424633	2	2	0	10	49	2335254	1	1	0	11	23	2324544	1	1	0
9	76	2426334	2	2	0	10	50	2335425	1	1	0	11	24	2325444	2	2	1
9	77	2426343	1	1	0	10	51	2335524	1	1	0	11	25	2342445	3	3	2
9	78	2426433	2	2	0	10	52	2342355	3	3	1	11	26	2342454	1	1	0
9	79	2432436	0	0	0	10	53	2342535	3	3	1	11	27	2342544	1	1	0
9	80	2432463	1	1	0	10	54	2342553	2	2	0	11	28	2344245	3	3	2
9	81	2432634	1	1	0	10	55	2343255	4	4	1	11	29	2344254	1	1	0
9	82	2432643	1	1	0	10	56	2343525	3	3	1	11	30	2344425	2	2	1
9	83	2433246	2	2	0	10	57	2345235	4	4	1	11	31	2344524	0	0	0
9	84	2433264	3	3	0	10	58	2345253	2	2	0	11	32	2345244	2	2	0
9	85	2433426	3	3	2	10	59	2345325	3	3	1	11	33	2345424	1	1	0
9	86	2434263	0	0	0	10	60	2352354	4	4	1	11	34	2352444	4	4	2
9	87	2434326	2	2	1	10	61	2352435	4	4	1	11	35	2354244	4	4	2
9	88	2442633	2	2	0	10	62	2352453	3	3	1	11	36	2354424	3	3	2
9	89	2443263	1	1	0	10	63	2352534	3	3	1	11	37	2424345	1	1	0
9	90	2443326	3	3	1	10	64	2352543	2	2	0	11	38	2424354	2	2	0
						10	65	2353245	3	3	1	11	39	2424435	3	3	2
						10	66	2353254	3	3	1	11	40	2424453	3	3	2
H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	10	67	2353425	2	2	0	11	41	2424534	2	2	0
						10	68	2353524	2	2	1	11	42	2424543	1	1	0
10	1	2233455	3	3	2	10	69	2354253	3	3	1	11	43	2425344	3	3	2
10	2	2233545	1	1	0	10	70	2354325	3	3	1	11	44	2425434	1	1	0
10	3	2233554	2	2	1	10	71	2355243	2	2	0	11	45	2425443	0	0	0
10	4	2234355	2	2	1	10	72	2355324	3	3	1	11	46	2432445	1	1	0
10	5	2234535	1	1	0	10	73	2425335	2	2	1	11	47	2432454	1	1	0
10	6	2234553	3	3	1	10	74	2425353	2	2	1	11	48	2432544	3	3	2
10	7	2235345	1	1	0	10	75	2425533	1	1	0	11	49	2434245	1	1	0
10	8	2235354	1	1	0	10	76	2432535	3	3	1	11	50	2434254	1	1	0
10	9	2235435	2	2	1	10	77	2432553	3	3	1	11	51	2434425	1	1	0
10	10	2235453	3	3	1	10	78	2433255	3	3	0	11	52	2435244	4	4	2
10	11	2235534	2	2	0	10	79	2433525	2	2	0	11	53	2442453	4	4	2
10	12	2235543	3	3	1	10	80	2435253	3	3	1	11	54	2442534	4	4	2
10	13	2243355	2	2	1	10	81	2435325	2	2	0	11	55	2442543	2	2	0
10	14	2243535	1	1	0	10	82	2452533	1	1	0	11	56	2443245	1	1	0
10	15	2243553	2	2	0	10	83	2453253	4	4	1	11	57	2443254	3	3	2
10	16	2245335	1	1	0	10	84	2453325	1	1	0	11	58	2443425	1	1	0
10	17	2245353	1	1	0	10	85	2525334	2	2	0	11	59	2444253	4	4	2
10	18	2245533	2	2	1	10	86	2525343	3	3	1	11	60	2444325	2	2	1
10	19	2253345	2	2	0	10	87	2525433	2	2	0						
10	20	2253354	1	1	0	10	88	2532534	4	4	1						
10	21	2253435	3	3	1	10	89	2532543	4	4	1	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF
10	22	2253453	2	2	1	10	90	2533254	2	2	1	12	1	2244444	2	2	1
10	23	2253534	1	1	0						12	2	2424444	4	4	3	
10	24	2253543	1	1	0						12	3	2442444	6	6	5	
10	25	2254335	2	2	0	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF						
10	26	2254353	1	1	0												
10	27	2254533	1	1	0	11	1	2234445	0	0	0						
10	28	2255334	2	2	1	11	2	2234454	0	0	0						
10	29	2255343	2	2	1	11	3	2234544	1	1	0						
10	30	2255433	3	3	2	11	4	2235444	2	2	1						

H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	15	15	2343435	4	4	2	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF
13	1	2333346	2	2	0	15	16	2343453	2	2	1	17	1	3333336	0	0	0
13	2	2333364	1	1	0	15	17	2343534	1	1	0						
13	3	2333436	2	2	0	15	18	2343543	1	1	0						
13	4	2333463	2	2	0	15	19	2344335	3	3	1						
13	5	2333634	0	0	0	15	20	2344353	1	1	0	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF
13	6	2333643	1	1	0	15	21	2344533	0	0	0	18	1	3333345	1	1	0
13	7	2333634	3	3	0	15	22	2345334	1	1	0	18	2	3333354	1	1	0
13	8	2334363	2	2	0	15	23	2345343	1	1	0	18	3	3333435	2	2	0
13	9	2334633	2	2	0	15	24	2345433	1	1	0	18	4	3333534	2	2	0
13	10	2336334	1	1	0	15	25	2353344	3	3	1	18	5	3334335	3	3	0
13	11	2336343	1	1	0	15	26	2353443	2	2	1	18	6	3335334	3	3	0
13	12	2336433	2	2	0	15	27	2354343	1	1	0						
13	13	2343336	2	2	0	15	28	2354334	3	3	2						
13	14	2343363	2	2	0	15	29	2354343	2	2	1	H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF
13	15	2343633	1	1	0	15	30	2354433	2	2	1	19	1	3333444	2	2	1
13	16	2346333	1	1	0	15	31	2433345	2	2	0	19	2	3334344	3	3	1
13	17	2363334	1	1	0	15	32	2433354	2	2	0	19	3	3334434	3	3	1
13	18	2363343	2	2	0	15	33	2433435	4	4	2	19	4	3343344	5	5	3
13	19	2363433	2	2	0	15	34	2433453	3	3	2	19	5	3343434	5	5	3
13	20	2364333	2	2	0	15	35	2433534	2	2	0						
13	21	2433336	1	1	0	15	36	2433543	1	1	0						
13	22	2433363	1	1	0	15	37	2434335	3	3	1						
13	23	2433633	1	1	0	15	38	2434353	2	2	1						
13	24	2436333	0	0	0	15	39	2434533	0	0	0						
13	25	2463333	1	1	0	15	40	2435334	2	2	0						
13	26	2633334	1	1	0	15	41	2435343	1	1	0						
13	27	2633343	2	2	0	15	42	2435433	1	1	0						
13	28	2633433	3	3	0	15	43	2443335	3	3	1						
13	29	2634333	2	2	0	15	44	2443353	3	3	1						
13	30	2643333	2	2	0	15	45	2443533	1	1	0						
						15	46	2445333	1	1	0						
						15	47	2453334	2	2	0						
H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF	15	48	2453343	2	2	0						
14	1	2333355	2	2	0	15	49	2453433	2	2	0						
14	2	2333535	2	2	0	15	50	2454333	1	1	0						
14	3	2333553	2	2	0	15	51	2533344	3	3	1						
14	4	2335335	2	2	0	15	52	2533434	3	3	1						
14	5	2335353	1	1	0	15	53	2533443	3	3	1						
14	6	2335533	1	1	0	15	54	2534334	4	4	2						
14	7	2353335	3	3	0	15	55	2534343	4	4	2						
14	8	2353353	2	2	0	15	56	2534433	3	3	1						
14	9	2353533	1	1	0	15	57	2543334	2	2	0						
14	10	2355333	2	2	0	15	58	2543343	4	4	2						
14	11	2533335	2	2	0	15	59	2543433	3	3	1						
14	12	2533353	3	3	0	15	60	2544333	2	2	1						
14	13	2533533	2	2	0							H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF
14	14	2535333	2	2	0							16	1	2334444	2	2	1
14	15	2553333	2	2	0							16	2	2343444	2	2	1
												16	3	2344344	1	1	0
H.	S.	value	5ths	4ths	FF							16	4	2344434	0	0	0
15	1	2333445	2	2	1							16	5	2344443	0	0	0
15	2	2333454	1	1	0							16	6	2433444	4	4	3
15	3	2333544	1	1	0							16	7	2434344	3	3	2
15	4	2334345	3	3	1							16	8	2434434	1	1	0
15	5	2334354	2	2	0							16	9	2434443	0	0	0
15	6	2334435	3	3	1							16	10	2443344	5	5	4
15	7	2334453	2	2	1							16	11	2443434	3	3	2
15	8	2334534	1	1	0							16	12	2443443	1	1	0
15	9	2334543	1	1	0							16	13	2444334	4	4	3
15	10	2335344	1	1	0							16	14	2444343	2	2	1
15	11	2335434	0	0	0							16	15	2444433	2	2	1
15	12	2335443	0	0	0												
15	13	2343345	4	4	2												
15	14	2343354	2	2	0												

III. SUB-SYSTEMS

Hyper-system No. 1 ; val.: 2 2 2 2 4 6 6

sys.: 15 ; 5ths: 58 ; 4ths: 58 ; FF: 21

(0; 1; 1; 2 2 2 2 4 6 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 4 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 4 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 4 6 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 6 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 1; 2; 2 2 2 2 6 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 6 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 6 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 6 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 6 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 1; 3; 2 2 2 2 6 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 6 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 6 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 6 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 6 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 6 4 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 1; 4; 2 2 2 4 2 6 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 2 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 6 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 6 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 2 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 1; 5; 2 2 2 4 6 2 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 6 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 2 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 6 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 1; 6; 2 2 2 6 2 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 2 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 4 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 6 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 1; 7; 2 2 2 6 2 6 4); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 2 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 6 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 6 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 6 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 1; 8; 2 2 2 6 4 2 6); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 2; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 6 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 1; 9; 2 2 2 6 6 2 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 6 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 6 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 6 2 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 2 6 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 6 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 1; 10; 2 2 4 2 2 6 6); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 2 6 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 2 6 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 2 6 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 2 6 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 6 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 1; 11; 2 2 4 2 6 2 6); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 6 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 6 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 6 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 1; 12; 2 2 4 6 2 2 6); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 2 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 2 6 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 2 6 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 1; 13; 2 2 6 2 2 6 4); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 2 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 2 6 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 1; 14; 2 2 6 2 4 2 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 10 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 2 6 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 1; 15; 2 2 6 2 6 2 4); 5th- 4; 4th- 4; FF- 1; Umin- no; Min- yes; Max- no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 6 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

Hyper-system No. 2 ; val.: 2 2 2 2 5 5 6

sys.: 15 ; 5ths: 23 ; 4ths: 23 ; FF 6

(0; 2; 1; 2 2 2 2 5 5 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 5 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 5 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 5 5 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 6 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 2; 2; 2 2 2 2 5 6 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 5 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 5 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 5 6 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 6 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 6 5 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 2; 3; 2 2 2 2 6 5 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 2 6 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 2 6 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 2 6 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 5 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 5 5 2 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 2; 4; 2 2 2 5 2 5 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 5 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 6 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 2; 5; 2 2 2 5 2 6 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 2 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 6 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 6 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 5 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 2; 6; 2 2 2 5 5 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 5 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 6 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 7; 2 2 2 5 6 2 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 6 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 2 5 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 8; 2 2 2 6 2 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 5 5 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 9; 2 2 2 6 5 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 5 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 2 5 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 10; 2 2 5 2 2 5 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 2 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 2 5 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 2 5 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 6 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 11; 2 2 5 2 2 6 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 2 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 2 6 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 2 6 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 5 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 12; 2 2 5 2 5 2 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 5 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 2; 13; 2 2 5 2 6 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 6 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 2; 14; 2 2 5 5 2 2 6); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 2 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 2 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 2 6 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 2; 15; 2 2 6 2 5 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 5 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 5 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
10 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

*Hyper-system No. 3 ; val.: 2 2 2 3 3 6 6***sys.: 30 ; 5ths: 54 ; 4ths: 54 ; FF 0**

(0; 3; 1; 2 2 2 3 3 6 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 3 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 3 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 3 6 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 6 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 2; 2 2 2 3 6 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 6 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 6 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 3 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 6 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 3; 2 2 2 3 6 6 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 6 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 6 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 6 3 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 6 3 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 3 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 4; 2 2 2 6 3 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 5; 2 2 2 6 3 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 6 3 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 6 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 6; 2 2 2 6 6 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 6 3 3 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 6 3 3 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 6 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 7; 2 2 3 2 3 6 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 3 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 3 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 3 6 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 6 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 6 2 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 8; 2 2 3 2 6 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 6 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 6 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 6 2 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 9; 2 2 3 2 6 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 6 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 6 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 6 3 2 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 6 3 2 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 10; 2 2 3 3 2 6 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 2 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 6 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 6 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 11; 2 2 3 3 6 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 6 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 6 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 12; 2 2 3 6 2 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

(0; 3; 24; 2 2 6 6 3 2 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 6 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 6 3 2 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 2 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 3 2 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 6 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 25; 2 3 2 3 2 6 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 2 6 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 2 6 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 2 6 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 6 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 6 2 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 3; 26; 2 3 2 3 6 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 6 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 6 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 27; 2 3 2 6 2 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 3 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 6 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 28; 2 3 2 6 2 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 6 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 29; 2 3 2 6 3 2 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 2 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 3; 30; 2 3 3 2 6 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 6 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 6 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 6 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 4 ; val.: 2 2 2 3 4 5 6***sys.: 120 ; 5ths: 208 ; 4ths: 208 ; FF: 60**

(0; 4; 1; 2 2 2 3 4 5 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 4 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 4 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 4 5 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 6 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 2; 2 2 2 3 4 6 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 4 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 4 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 4 6 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 6 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 5 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 3; 2 2 2 3 5 4 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 5 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 5 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 6 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 4; 2 2 2 3 5 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 5 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 5 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 6 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 6 4 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 3 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 5; 2 2 2 3 6 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 6 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 6 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 4 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 5 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 6; 2 2 2 3 6 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 6 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 6 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 5 3 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 5 3 2 2 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 4 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 13; 2 2 2 5 3 4 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 3 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 3 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 4 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 6 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 5 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 14; 2 2 2 5 3 6 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 3 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 3 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 6 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 6 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 5 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 15; 2 2 2 5 4 3 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 4 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 4 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 6 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 5 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 16; 2 2 2 5 4 6 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 4 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 4 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 6 3 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 5 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 17; 2 2 2 5 6 3 4); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 6 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 6 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 6 3 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 3 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 5 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 18; 2 2 2 5 6 4 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 6 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 6 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 6 4 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 4 3 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 5 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 19; 2 2 2 6 3 4 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 3 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 3 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 4 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 5 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 6 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 20; 2 2 2 6 3 5 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 3 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 3 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 5 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 5 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 6 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 21; 2 2 2 6 4 3 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 4 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 5 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 6 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 22; 2 2 2 6 4 5 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 4 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 5 3 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 6 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 23; 2 2 2 6 5 3 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 5 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 5 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 5 3 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 3 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 6 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 24; 2 2 2 6 5 4 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = yes; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 5 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 5 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 5 4 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 4 3 2 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 6 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 25; 2 2 3 2 4 5 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 4 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 4 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 5 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 6 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 6 2 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 26; 2 2 3 2 4 6 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 4 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 4 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 6 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 5 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 5 2 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 27; 2 2 3 2 5 4 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 5 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 5 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 4 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 6 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 6 2 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 28; 2 2 3 2 5 6 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 5 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 5 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 6 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 6 4 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 6 4 2 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 29; 2 2 3 2 6 4 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 6 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 6 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 4 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 5 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 5 2 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 30; 2 2 3 2 6 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 6 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 6 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 5 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 5 4 2 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 31; 2 2 3 4 2 5 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 5 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 6 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 32; 2 2 3 4 2 6 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 2 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 6 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 5 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 33; 2 2 3 4 5 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 5 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 34; 2 2 3 4 6 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 6 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 6 2 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 2 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 35; 2 2 3 5 2 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 36; 2 2 3 5 2 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 6 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 37; 2 2 3 5 4 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 38; 2 2 3 5 6 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 6 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 2 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 3 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 39; 2 2 3 6 2 4 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 2 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 40; 2 2 3 6 2 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 2 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 5 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 41; 2 2 3 6 4 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 4 2 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 42; 2 2 3 6 5 2 4); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 5 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 2 4 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 3 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 43; 2 2 4 2 3 5 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 3 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 3 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 3 5 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 6 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 44; 2 2 4 2 3 6 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 3 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 3 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 3 6 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 6 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 5 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 45; 2 2 4 2 5 3 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 5 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 5 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 6 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 46; 2 2 4 2 5 6 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 5 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 5 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 6 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 6 3 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 47; 2 2 4 2 6 3 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 6 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 6 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 5 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 48; 2 2 4 2 6 5 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 6 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 6 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 5 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 5 3 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 49; 2 2 4 3 2 5 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 2 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 5 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 6 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 50; 2 2 4 3 2 6 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 2 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 6 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 5 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 51; 2 2 4 3 5 2 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 5 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 52; 2 2 4 3 6 2 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 6 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 4 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 53; 2 2 4 5 2 3 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 2 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 3 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 6 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 54; 2 2 4 5 2 6 3); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 2 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 6 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 55; 2 2 4 5 3 2 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 3 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 2 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 6 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 56; 2 2 4 5 6 2 3); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 6 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 6 2 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 2 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 3 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 4 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 57; 2 2 4 6 2 3 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 2 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 3 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 5 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 58; 2 2 4 6 2 5 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 2 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 5 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 59; 2 2 4 6 3 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 3 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 2 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 4 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 60; 2 2 4 6 5 2 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 5 2 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 2 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 3 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 4 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4; 61; 2 2 5 2 3 4 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 3 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 3 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 3 4 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 4 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 2 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 62; 2 2 5 2 3 6 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 3 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 3 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 3 6 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 6 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 63; 2 2 5 2 4 3 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 4 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 4 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 64; 2 2 5 2 4 6 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 4 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 4 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4; 65; 2 2 5 2 6 3 4); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 6 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 6 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 6 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 66; 2 2 5 2 6 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 6 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 67; 2 2 5 3 2 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 6 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 68; 2 2 5 3 2 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 69; 2 2 5 3 4 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 4 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 6 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 70; 2 2 5 3 6 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 6 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 5 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 71; 2 2 5 4 2 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 3 6 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 6 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 72; 2 2 5 4 2 6 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 73; 2 2 5 4 3 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 2 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 6 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 74; 2 2 5 4 6 2 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 6 2 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 2 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 3 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 5 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 75; 2 2 5 6 2 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 6 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 6 2 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 3 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 4 2 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 76; 2 2 5 6 2 4 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 6 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 6 2 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 3 2 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 77; 2 2 5 6 3 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 6 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 6 3 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 2 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 4 2 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 5 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 78; 2 2 5 6 4 2 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 6 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 6 4 2 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 3 2 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 5 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 79; 2 2 6 2 3 4 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 3 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 4 5 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 80; 2 2 6 2 3 5 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 3 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 81; 2 2 6 2 4 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 5 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 82; 2 2 6 2 4 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 83; 2 2 6 2 5 3 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 5 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 84; 2 2 6 2 5 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 5 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 85; 2 2 6 3 2 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 2 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 5 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 86; 2 2 6 3 2 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 2 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 87; 2 2 6 3 4 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 4 2 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 5 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 88; 2 2 6 3 5 2 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 5 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 6 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 95; 2 2 6 5 3 2 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 5 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 5 3 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 4 2 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 6 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 96; 2 2 6 5 4 2 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 5 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 5 4 2 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 3 2 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 6 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 97; 2 3 2 4 2 5 6); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 5 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 6 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 98; 2 3 2 4 2 6 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 2 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 6 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 5 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4; 99; 2 3 2 4 5 2 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 5 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4; 100; 2 3 2 4 6 2 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 6 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 2 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;101; 2 3 2 5 2 4 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;102; 2 3 2 5 2 6 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 6 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;103; 2 3 2 5 4 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;104; 2 3 2 5 6 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 6 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 2 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 2 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 4;105; 2 3 2 6 2 4 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;106; 2 3 2 6 2 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 5 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 4;107; 2 3 2 6 4 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;108; 2 3 2 6 5 2 4); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 5 2 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 2 4 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 4;109; 2 3 4 2 5 2 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 5 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 2 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 6 2 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;110; 2 3 4 2 6 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 5 2 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;111; 2 3 5 2 4 2 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 2 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 2 6 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;112; 2 3 5 2 6 2 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 6 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 6 2 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 4 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;119; 2 4 3 2 5 2 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 5 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 5 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 6 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 6 2 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 4 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 4;120; 2 4 3 2 6 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 6 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 2 5 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

Hyper-system No. 5 ; val.: 2 2 2 3 5 5 5

sys.: 20 ; 5ths: 56 ; 4ths: 56 ; FF: 12

(0; 5; 1; 2 2 2 3 5 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 3 5 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 3 5 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 5 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 5 2 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 5; 2; 2 2 2 5 3 5 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 5 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 5; 3; 2 2 2 5 5 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 3 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 5; 4; 2 2 2 5 5 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 5 3 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 2 5 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 5; 5; 2 2 3 2 5 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 2 5 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 2 5 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 5 2 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 5; 6; 2 2 3 5 2 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 2 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 5 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 7; 2 2 3 5 5 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 5 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 5 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 8; 2 2 5 2 3 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 3 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 3 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 9; 2 2 5 2 5 3 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 5 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 5; 10; 2 2 5 2 5 5 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 5 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 5 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 11; 2 2 5 3 2 5 5); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 12; 2 2 5 3 5 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 5 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 5; 13; 2 2 5 5 2 3 5); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 2 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 3 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 5 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 14; 2 2 5 5 2 5 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 2 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 15; 2 2 5 5 3 2 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 3 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 5 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 16; 2 2 5 5 5 2 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 5 2 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 3 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 3 2 2 5 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 17; 2 3 2 5 2 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 18; 2 3 2 5 5 2 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 5; 19; 2 3 5 2 5 2 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 5 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 5; 20; 2 5 2 5 2 5 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 2 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 2 5 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

Hyper-system No. 6 ; val.: 2 2 2 4 4 4 6

sys.: 20 ; 5ths: 80 ; 4ths: 80 ; FF: 46

(0; 6; 1; 2 2 2 4 4 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 4 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 6 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 6 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 6; 2; 2 2 2 4 4 6 4); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=4; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 4 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 6 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 4 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 6; 3; 2 2 2 4 6 4 4); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=4; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 6 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 4 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 4 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 6; 4; 2 2 2 6 4 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 6 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 6 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 4 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 6; 5; 2 2 4 2 4 4 6); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=4; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 4 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 6 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 6 2 2 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 6; 6; 2 2 4 2 4 6 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 4 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 4 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 13; 2 2 4 6 4 2 4); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 3; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 4 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 4 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 4 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 14; 2 2 6 2 4 4 4); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 2 4 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 2 4 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 4 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 4 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 15; 2 2 6 4 2 4 4); 5th = 5; 4th = 5; FF = 3; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 4 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 4 2 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 2 4 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 4 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 16; 2 2 6 4 4 2 4); 5th = 5; 4th = 5; FF = 4; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 4 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 4 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 4 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 4 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 6 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 17; 2 4 2 4 2 4 6); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 2 4 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 2 4 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 4 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 6 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 18; 2 4 2 4 2 6 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 2 6 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 2 6 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 6 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 19; 2 4 2 4 4 2 6); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

10 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 6 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 4 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 2 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 6; 20; 2 4 2 6 2 4 4); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

11 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 6 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 6 2 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 2 4 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 4 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 6 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

Hyper-system No. 7 ; val.: 2 2 2 4 4 5 5

sys.: 30 ; 5ths: 40 ; 4ths: 40 ; FF: 14

(0; 7; 1; 2 2 2 4 4 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 4 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 4 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 5 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 5 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 7; 2; 2 2 2 4 5 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 5 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 5 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 4 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 5 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 3; 2 2 2 4 5 5 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 4 5 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 4 5 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 5 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 4 2 2 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 4 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 7; 4; 2 2 2 5 4 4 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 5 2 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 5; 2 2 2 5 4 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 5 4 2 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 5 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 6; 2 2 2 5 5 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=yes; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 2 5 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 2 5 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=yes; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 4 4 2 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = yes; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 7; 2 2 4 2 4 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 4 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 4 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 5 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 8; 2 2 4 2 5 4 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 5 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 5 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 4 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 5 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 9; 2 2 4 2 5 5 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 2 5 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 5 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 4 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 4 2 2 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 10; 2 2 4 4 2 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 11; 2 2 4 4 5 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 5 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 4 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 12; 2 2 4 5 2 4 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 5 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 13; 2 2 4 5 2 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 14; 2 2 4 5 4 2 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 4 2 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 5 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 15; 2 2 4 5 5 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 5 2 4 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 4 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 7; 16; 2 2 5 2 4 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 5 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 17; 2 2 5 2 4 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 7; 18; 2 2 5 2 5 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 2 5 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 4 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 19; 2 2 5 4 2 4 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 4 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 20; 2 2 5 4 2 5 4); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 2 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 5 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 21; 2 2 5 4 4 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 4 2 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 5 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 2 5 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 22; 2 2 5 4 5 2 4); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 5 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 5 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 23; 2 2 5 5 2 4 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 2 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 2 4 4 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 24; 2 2 5 5 4 2 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 2; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 4 2 4 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 4 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 25; 2 4 2 4 2 5 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 2 5 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 7; 26; 2 4 2 4 5 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 27; 2 4 2 5 2 4 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 4 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 28; 2 4 2 5 2 5 4); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 2 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 2 5 4 2 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 4 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 29; 2 4 2 5 4 2 5); 5th = 0; 4th = 0; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 5 2 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 7; 30; 2 4 4 2 5 2 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 5 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 2 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

Hyper-system No. 8 ; val.: 2 2 3 3 3 5 6

sys.: 60 ; 5ths: 120 ; 4ths: 120 ; FF 0

(0; 8; 1; 2 2 3 3 3 5 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 3 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 3 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 5 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 6 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 2; 2 2 3 3 3 6 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 3 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 3 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 6 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 5 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 3; 2 2 3 3 5 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 5 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 5 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 6 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 4; 2 2 3 3 5 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 5 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 5 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 6 3 2 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 6 3 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 3 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 5; 2 2 3 3 6 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 6 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 6 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 3 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 5 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 6; 2 2 3 3 6 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 6 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 6 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 5 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 5 3 2 2 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 3 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 3 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 7; 2 2 3 5 3 3 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 3 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 3 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 6 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 8; 2 2 3 5 3 6 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 3 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 3 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 6 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 5 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 9; 2 2 3 5 6 3 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 6 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 6 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 6 3 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 3 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 5 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 10; 2 2 3 6 3 3 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 3 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 5 2 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 3 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 11; 2 2 3 6 3 5 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 3 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 5 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 3 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 6 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 12; 2 2 3 6 5 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 5 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 3 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 2 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 3 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 6 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 13; 2 2 5 3 3 3 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 3 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 3 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 3 6 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 6 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 14; 2 2 5 3 3 6 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 3 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 3 6 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 6 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 3 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 15; 2 2 5 3 6 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 6 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 6 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 3 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 5 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 3 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 16; 2 2 5 6 3 3 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 6 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 6 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 6 3 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 2 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 5 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 17; 2 2 6 3 3 3 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 3 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 5 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 6 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 18; 2 2 6 3 3 5 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 3 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 3 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 6 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 19; 2 2 6 3 5 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 5 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 3 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 2 6 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 6 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 20; 2 2 6 5 3 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 5 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 5 3 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 3 2 2 6; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 2 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 6 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 21; 2 3 2 3 3 5 6); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 3 5 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 3 5 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 3 5 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 6 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 6 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 3 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 22; 2 3 2 3 3 6 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 3 6 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 3 6 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 3 6 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 5 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 3 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 3 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 8; 23; 2 3 2 3 5 3 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 5 3 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 5 3 6 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 3 6 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 6 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 6 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 30; 2 3 2 6 3 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 31; 2 3 2 6 3 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 5 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 6 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 32; 2 3 2 6 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 5 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 5 3 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 2 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 6 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 33; 2 3 3 2 3 5 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 3 5 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 3 5 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 3 5 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 6 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 6 2 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 34; 2 3 3 2 3 6 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 3 6 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 3 6 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 3 6 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 6 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 5 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 5 2 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 8; 35; 2 3 3 2 5 3 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 5 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 5 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 6 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 42; 2 3 3 3 6 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 6 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 5 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 43; 2 3 3 5 2 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 3 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 6 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 44; 2 3 3 5 2 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 6 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 45; 2 3 3 5 3 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 46; 2 3 3 6 2 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 2 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 3 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 5 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 47; 2 3 3 6 2 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 2 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 5 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 54; 2 3 6 2 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 2 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 2 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 5 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 6 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 6 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 55; 2 3 6 3 2 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 2 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 6 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 56; 2 3 6 3 3 2 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 2 5 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 57; 2 5 2 6 3 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 2 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 2 6 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 3 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 5 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 58; 2 5 3 2 6 3 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 2 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 3 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 8; 59; 2 5 3 3 2 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 6 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 8; 60; 2 5 3 3 3 2 6); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 3 2 6; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 3 2 6 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 2 6 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 2 6 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 5 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

*Hyper-system No. 9; val.: 2 2 3 3 4 4 6***sys.: 90 ; 5ths: 168 ; 4ths: 168 ; FF: 54**

(0; 9; 1; 2 2 3 3 4 4 6); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 4 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 6 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 2; 2 2 3 3 4 6 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 4 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 6 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 4 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 3; 2 2 3 3 6 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 6 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 4 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 4 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 4; 2 2 3 4 3 4 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 4 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 5; 2 2 3 4 3 6 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 6 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 6 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 6; 2 2 3 4 4 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 6 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 7; 2 2 3 4 4 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 6 3 2 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 8; 2 2 3 4 6 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 6 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 3 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 9; 2 2 3 4 6 4 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 6 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 4 3 2 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 10; 2 2 3 6 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 11; 2 2 3 6 4 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 4 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 12; 2 2 3 6 4 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 6 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 6 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 4 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 6 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 4 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 19; 2 2 4 4 3 3 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 3 6 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 6 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 10 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 2 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 20; 2 2 4 4 3 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 6 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 6 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 21; 2 2 4 4 6 3 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 6 3 3 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 3 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 22; 2 2 4 6 3 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 3 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 23; 2 2 4 6 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 3 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 24; 2 2 4 6 4 3 3); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 6 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 6 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 4 3 3 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 25; 2 2 6 3 3 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 26; 2 2 6 3 4 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 4 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 27; 2 2 6 3 4 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 3 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 4 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 28; 2 2 6 4 3 3 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 4 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 3 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 4 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 6 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 29; 2 2 6 4 3 4 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 4 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 3 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 30; 2 2 6 4 4 3 3); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 6 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 6 4 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 4 3 3 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 3 2 2 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 6 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 31; 2 3 2 3 4 4 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 4 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 4 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 6 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 32; 2 3 2 3 4 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 4 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 4 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 6 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 4 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 33; 2 3 2 3 6 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 6 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 6 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 4 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 4 2 3 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 34; 2 3 2 4 3 4 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 3 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 35; 2 3 2 4 3 6 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 3 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 6 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 36; 2 3 2 4 4 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 6 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 37; 2 3 2 4 4 6 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 6 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 38; 2 3 2 4 6 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 3 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 39; 2 3 2 4 6 4 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 4 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 40; 2 3 2 6 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 41; 2 3 2 6 4 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 42; 2 3 2 6 4 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 6 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 6 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 4 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 43; 2 3 3 2 4 4 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 4 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 4 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 6 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 44; 2 3 3 2 4 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 4 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 4 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 4 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 45; 2 3 3 2 6 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 6 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 6 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 4 2 3 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 46; 2 3 3 4 2 4 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 47; 2 3 3 4 2 6 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 48; 2 3 3 4 4 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 49; 2 3 3 4 6 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 6 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 2 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 50; 2 3 3 6 2 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 2 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 51; 2 3 3 6 4 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 4 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 2 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 52; 2 3 4 2 3 4 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 3 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 4 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 53; 2 3 4 2 3 6 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 3 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 6 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 54; 2 3 4 2 4 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 55; 2 3 4 2 4 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 56; 2 3 4 2 6 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 57; 2 3 4 2 6 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 58; 2 3 4 3 2 4 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 59; 2 3 4 3 2 6 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 60; 2 3 4 3 4 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 61; 2 3 4 3 6 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 6 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 2 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 2 4 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 62; 2 3 4 4 2 3 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 3 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 6 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 63; 2 3 4 4 2 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 64; 2 3 4 4 3 2 6); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 2 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 65; 2 3 4 6 2 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 6 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 2 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 2 4 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 3 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 66; 2 3 4 6 3 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 6 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 3 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 2 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 4 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 67; 2 3 6 2 4 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 2 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 68; 2 3 6 2 4 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 2 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 2 4 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 6 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 69; 2 3 6 3 2 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 2 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 70; 2 3 6 3 4 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 4 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 71; 2 3 6 4 2 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 4 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 2 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 3 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 3 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 6 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 72; 2 3 6 4 3 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 4 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 4 3 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 4 2 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 73; 2 4 2 4 3 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 3 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 6 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 2 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 74; 2 4 2 4 3 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 3 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 6 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 75; 2 4 2 4 6 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 6 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 3 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 76; 2 4 2 6 3 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

10 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 6 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 6 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 77; 2 4 2 6 3 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 6 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 6 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 3 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 78; 2 4 2 6 4 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 6 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 6 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 6 4 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 79; 2 4 3 2 4 3 6); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 3 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 80; 2 4 3 2 4 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 6 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 81; 2 4 3 2 6 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 82; 2 4 3 2 6 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 6 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 4 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 83; 2 4 3 3 2 4 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 3 2 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 4 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 6 2 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 84; 2 4 3 3 2 6 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 3 2 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 6 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 4 2 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 85; 2 4 3 3 4 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 3 4 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 6 2 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 86; 2 4 3 4 2 6 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 4 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 6 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 87; 2 4 3 4 3 2 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 4 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 6 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 88; 2 4 4 2 6 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 6 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 6 3 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 89; 2 4 4 3 2 6 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 2 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 6 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 6 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 6 3 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 9; 90; 2 4 4 3 3 2 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
10 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 3 2 6 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 2 6 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 2 6 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 6 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 6 2 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 4 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 10; val.: 2 2 3 3 4 5 5***sys.: 90 ; 5ths: 210 ; 4ths: 210 ; FF: 54**

(0; 10; 1; 2 2 3 3 4 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 4 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 4 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 5 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 2; 2 2 3 3 5 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 5 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 5 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 5 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 3; 2 2 3 3 5 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 3 5 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 3 5 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 5 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 4 2 2 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 4; 2 2 3 4 3 5 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 5 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 5; 2 2 3 4 5 3 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 6; 2 2 3 4 5 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 4 3 2 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 3 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 13; 2 2 4 3 3 5 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 3 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 5 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 2 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 14; 2 2 4 3 5 3 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 5 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 15; 2 2 4 3 5 5 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 5 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 5 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 5 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 16; 2 2 4 5 3 3 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 3 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 3 5 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 5 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 17; 2 2 4 5 3 5 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 3 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 5 3 2 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 5 3 2 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 18; 2 2 4 5 5 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = yes; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 5 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 25; 2 2 5 4 3 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 5 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 5 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 26; 2 2 5 4 3 5 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 27; 2 2 5 4 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 4 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 5 3 3 2 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 5 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 28; 2 2 5 5 3 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 3 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 29; 2 2 5 5 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 3 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 3 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 30; 2 2 5 5 4 3 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 5 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 5 4 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 4 3 3 2 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 3 2 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 5 5 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = yes; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 31; 2 3 2 3 4 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 4 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 4 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 4 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 5 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 2 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 3 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 32; 2 3 2 3 5 4 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 5 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 5 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 4 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 5 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 3 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 33; 2 3 2 3 5 5 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 3 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 3 5 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 3 5 5 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 5 4 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 4 2 3 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 2 3 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 34; 2 3 2 4 3 5 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 3 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 3 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 3 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 35; 2 3 2 4 5 3 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 5 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 3 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 5 2 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 36; 2 3 2 4 5 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 4 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 4 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 5 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 4 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 37; 2 3 2 5 3 4 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 38; 2 3 2 5 3 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 5 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 39; 2 3 2 5 4 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 5 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 40; 2 3 2 5 4 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 5 3 2 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 5 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 41; 2 3 2 5 5 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 3 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 42; 2 3 2 5 5 4 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 5 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 5 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 4 3 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 4 3 2 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 43; 2 3 3 2 4 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 4 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 4 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 5 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 5 2 3 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 44; 2 3 3 2 5 4 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 5 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 5 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 4 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 5 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 5 2 3 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 45; 2 3 3 2 5 5 4); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 2 5 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 2 5 5 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 5 4 2 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 4 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 4 2 3 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 46; 2 3 3 4 2 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 5 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 5 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 3 3 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 47; 2 3 3 4 5 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 2 5 2 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 5 2 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 3 3 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 3 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 48; 2 3 3 5 2 4 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 49; 2 3 3 5 2 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 50; 2 3 3 5 4 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 51; 2 3 3 5 5 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 5 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 2 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 52; 2 3 4 2 3 5 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 3 5 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 53; 2 3 4 2 5 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 54; 2 3 4 2 5 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 55; 2 3 4 3 2 5 5); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 2 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 5 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 56; 2 3 4 3 5 2 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 5 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 57; 2 3 4 5 2 3 5); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 3 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 3 5 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 58; 2 3 4 5 2 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 59; 2 3 4 5 3 2 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 60; 2 3 5 2 3 5 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 3 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 3 5 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 61; 2 3 5 2 4 3 5); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 3 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 62; 2 3 5 2 4 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 63; 2 3 5 2 5 3 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 64; 2 3 5 2 5 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 65; 2 3 5 3 2 4 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 66; 2 3 5 3 2 5 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 67; 2 3 5 3 4 2 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 4 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 68; 2 3 5 3 5 2 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 5 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 69; 2 3 5 4 2 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 4 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 70; 2 3 5 4 3 2 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 4 3 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 71; 2 3 5 5 2 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 5 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 2 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 3 2 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 72; 2 3 5 5 3 2 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 5 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 3 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 4 2 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 73; 2 4 2 5 3 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 2 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 74; 2 4 2 5 3 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 5 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 75; 2 4 2 5 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 5 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 3 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 2 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 10; 76; 2 4 3 2 5 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 77; 2 4 3 2 5 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 5 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 5 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 5 3 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 78; 2 4 3 3 2 5 5); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 3 2 5 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 5 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 5 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 5 2 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 4 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

(0; 10; 79; 2 4 3 3 5 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 3 5 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 2 5 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 5 2 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 80; 2 4 3 5 2 5 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 5 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 5 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 5 3 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 3 5 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 81; 2 4 3 5 3 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 5 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 2 5 2 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 4 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 82; 2 4 5 2 5 3 3); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 5 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 5 2 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 5 3 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 3 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 4 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 83; 2 4 5 3 2 5 3); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 5 3 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 5 3 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 2 5 3 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 3 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 84; 2 4 5 3 3 2 5); 5th = 1; 4th = 1; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 5 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 5 3 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 2 5 2 4 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 4 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 85; 2 5 2 5 3 3 4); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 2 5 3 3 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 2 5 3 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 3 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 4 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 5 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 86; 2 5 2 5 3 4 3); 5th = 3; 4th = 3; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 2 5 3 4 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 2 5 3 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 4 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 5 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 2 5 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 87; 2 5 2 5 4 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 2 5 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 2 5 4 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 5 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 2 5 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 88; 2 5 3 2 5 3 4); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 2 5 3 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 2 5 3 4 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 3 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 10 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 4 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 5 3 2; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 5 3 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 10; 89; 2 5 3 2 5 4 3); 5th = 4; 4th = 4; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 2 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 3 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 5 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 10; 90; 2 5 3 3 2 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 2 5 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 5 3 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 11 ; val.: 2 2 3 4 4 4 5***sys.: 60 ; 5ths: 96 ; 4ths: 96 ; FF: 36**

(0; 11; 1; 2 2 3 4 4 4 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 5 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 2; 2 2 3 4 4 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 5 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 3; 2 2 3 4 5 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 4 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 4 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 4 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 4; 2 2 3 5 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 3 5 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 3 5 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 4 2 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 3 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 5; 2 2 4 3 4 4 5); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 5 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 6; 2 2 4 3 4 5 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 7; 2 2 4 3 5 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 3 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 3 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 8; 2 2 4 4 3 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 4 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 5 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 9; 2 2 4 4 3 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 5 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 10; 2 2 4 4 4 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 3 5 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 5 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 2 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 11; 2 2 4 4 4 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 5 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 5 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 12; 2 2 4 4 5 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 5 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 13; 2 2 4 4 5 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 5 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 4 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 14; 2 2 4 5 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 15; 2 2 4 5 4 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 4 3 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 16; 2 2 4 5 4 4 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 5 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 5 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 4 4 3 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 3 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 2 4 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 17; 2 2 5 3 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 5 3 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 4 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 4 2 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 5 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 18; 2 2 5 4 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 5 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 2 5 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 2 5 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 4 2 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 25; 2 3 4 2 4 4 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 26; 2 3 4 2 4 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 27; 2 3 4 2 5 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 2 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 28; 2 3 4 4 2 4 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 29; 2 3 4 4 2 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 30; 2 3 4 4 4 2 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 2 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 31; 2 3 4 4 5 2 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 5 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 5 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 2 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 2 4 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 32; 2 3 4 5 2 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 2 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 33; 2 3 4 5 4 2 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 4 2 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 2 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 4 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 4 2 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 34; 2 3 5 2 4 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 2 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 2 4 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 35; 2 3 5 4 2 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 4 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 2 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 42; 2 4 2 4 5 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 5 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 4 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 43; 2 4 2 5 3 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 3 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 44; 2 4 2 5 4 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 45; 2 4 2 5 4 4 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 5 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 5 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 5 4 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 3 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 46; 2 4 3 2 4 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 47; 2 4 3 2 4 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 4 5 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 48; 2 4 3 2 5 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 2 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 2 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 2 5 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 49; 2 4 3 4 2 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 4 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 4 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 50; 2 4 3 4 2 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 4 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 2 5 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 51; 2 4 3 4 4 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 4 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 2 5 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 52; 2 4 3 5 2 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 5 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 2 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 2 4 4 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 4 2 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 53; 2 4 4 2 4 5 3); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 5 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 54; 2 4 4 2 5 3 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 3 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 55; 2 4 4 2 5 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 5 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 5 4 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 56; 2 4 4 3 2 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 2 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 4 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 4 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 4 5 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 57; 2 4 4 3 2 5 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 2 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 2 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 2 5 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 2 5 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 4 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 4 3 2 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 58; 2 4 4 3 4 2 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 4 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 4 2 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 2 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 2 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 2 5 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 11; 59; 2 4 4 4 2 5 3); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 4 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 4 2 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 2 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 2 5 3 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 10 sub-system N° 5; value: 2 5 3 2 4 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 4 4 2; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 4 2 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 11; 60; 2 4 4 4 3 2 5); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 4 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 4 3 2 5 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 2 5 2 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 2 5 2 4 4; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 2 5 2 4 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 2 5 2 4 4 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 4 4 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

Hyper-system No. 12 ; val.: 2 2 4 4 4 4 4

sys.: 3 ; 5ths: 12 ; 4ths: 12 ; FF 9

(0; 12; 1; 2 2 4 4 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=yes; Max=no
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 2 4 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 2 4 4 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 4 4 2 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 4 2 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=yes
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 2 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=yes; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 12; 2; 2 4 2 4 4 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 2 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 2 4 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 3; value: 2 4 4 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 4 2 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 12; 3; 2 4 4 2 4 4 4); 5th=6; 4th=6; FF=5; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
11 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 2 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 2 4 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 4; value: 2 4 4 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 4 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 13; val.: 2 3 3 3 3 4 6***sys.: 30 ; 5ths: 46 ; 4ths: 46 ; FF 0**

(0; 13; 1; 2 3 3 3 3 4 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 4 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 4 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 6 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 6 2 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 2; 2 3 3 3 3 6 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 6 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 6 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 4 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 4 2 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 3; 2 3 3 3 4 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 6 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 4; 2 3 3 3 4 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 6 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 6 3 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 5; 2 3 3 3 6 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 6 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 3 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 4 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 6; 2 3 3 3 6 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 6 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 6 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 4 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 4 3 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 7; 2 3 3 4 3 3 6); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 6 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 8; 2 3 3 4 3 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 6 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 9; 2 3 3 4 6 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 6 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 6 3 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 10; 2 3 3 6 3 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 11; 2 3 3 6 3 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 4 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 12; 2 3 3 6 4 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 6 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 6 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 4 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 4 3 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 3 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 13; 2 3 4 3 3 3 6); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 3 3 6 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 3 6 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 6 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 6 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 2 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 2 3 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 14; 2 3 4 3 3 6 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 3 6 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 6 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 6 3 2 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 15; 2 3 4 3 6 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 6 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 6 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 6 3 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 6 3 3 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 16; 2 3 4 6 3 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 6 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 6 3 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 3 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 17; 2 3 6 3 3 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 4 2 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 18; 2 3 6 3 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 6 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 6 3 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 6 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 6 3 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 6 3 3 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 4 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 25; 2 4 6 3 3 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 6 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 6 3 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 6 3 3 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 3 2 4 6; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 4 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 26; 2 6 3 3 3 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 6 3 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 6 3 3 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 3 4 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 4 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 6 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 27; 2 6 3 3 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 6 3 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 6 3 3 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 4 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 6 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 28; 2 6 3 3 4 3 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 6 3 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 6 3 3 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 6 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 6 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 29; 2 6 3 4 3 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 6 3 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 6 3 4 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 3 2 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 6 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 6 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 6 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 13; 30; 2 6 4 3 3 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 6 4 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 2; value: 6 4 3 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
10 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 3 3 2 6; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 3 2 6 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 6 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
10 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 6 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 6 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 14; val.: 2 3 3 3 3 5 5***sys.: 15 ; 5ths: 29 ; 4ths: 29 ; FF 0**

(0; 14; 1; 2 3 3 3 3 5 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 5 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 5 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 5 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 5 2 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 14; 2; 2 3 3 3 5 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 5 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 5 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 3; 2 3 3 3 5 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 5 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 5 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 5 3 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 14; 4; 2 3 3 5 3 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 5; 2 3 3 5 3 5 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 5 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 6; 2 3 3 5 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 5 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 5 3 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 14; 7; 2 3 5 3 3 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 5 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 8; 2 3 5 3 3 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 9; 2 3 5 3 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 5 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 5 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 10; 2 3 5 5 3 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=yes
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 5 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 5 3 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 3 5 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 5 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=yes; M347=no

(0; 14; 11; 2 5 3 3 3 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 3 5 2 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 5 2 5 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 5 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 14; 12; 2 5 3 3 3 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 5 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 3 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 14; 13; 2 5 3 3 5 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 3 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 3 5 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 3 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 3 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 14; 14; 2 5 3 5 3 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 3 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 3 5 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 3 2 5 3; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 5 3 5; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 3 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 3 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 14; 15; 2 5 5 3 3 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 0; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = yes

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 5 3 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 5 3 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 3 2 5 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 5 5 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 5 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 5 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = yes; M347 = no

Hyper-system No. 15; val.: 2 3 3 3 4 4 5

sys.: 60 ; 5ths: 120 ; 4ths: 120 ; FF: 36

(0; 15; 1; 2 3 3 3 4 4 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 5 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 2; 2 3 3 3 4 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 4 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 3; 2 3 3 3 5 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 3 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 5 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 4 2 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 4; 2 3 3 4 3 4 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 5; 2 3 3 4 3 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 6; 2 3 3 4 4 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 5 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 7; 2 3 3 4 4 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 5 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 8; 2 3 3 4 5 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 9; 2 3 3 4 5 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 5 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 4 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 10; 2 3 3 5 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 11; 2 3 3 5 4 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 12; 2 3 3 5 4 4 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 5 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 4 3 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 3 5 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 13; 2 3 4 3 3 4 5); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 3 4 5 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 4 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 2 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 14; 2 3 4 3 3 5 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 3 5 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 5 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 2 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 15; 2 3 4 3 4 3 5); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 4 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 16; 2 3 4 3 4 5 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 4 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 5 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 5 3 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 17; 2 3 4 3 5 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 5 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 18; 2 3 4 3 5 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 5 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 4 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 4 3 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 19; 2 3 4 4 3 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 3 5 2 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 5 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 3 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 20; 2 3 4 4 3 5 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 5 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 5 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 21; 2 3 4 4 5 3 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 5 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 5 3 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 22; 2 3 4 5 3 3 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 23; 2 3 4 5 3 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 4 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 24; 2 3 4 5 4 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 5 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 5 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 4 3 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 3 4 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 25; 2 3 5 3 3 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 26; 2 3 5 3 4 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 4 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 27; 2 3 5 3 4 4 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 3 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 4 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 28; 2 3 5 4 3 3 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=2; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 4 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 4 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 5 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 29; 2 3 5 4 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 5 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 5 4 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 4 3 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 3 2 3 5; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 5 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 30; 2 3 5 4 4 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

(0; 15; 42; 2 4 3 5 4 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 5 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 3 5 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 4 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 4 3 3 2 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 43; 2 4 4 3 3 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 3 3 5 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 3 5 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 5 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 2 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 2 4 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 44; 2 4 4 3 3 5 3); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 3 5 3 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 5 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 3 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 3 2 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 45; 2 4 4 3 5 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 5 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 5 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 3 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 46; 2 4 4 5 3 3 3); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 5 3 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 5 3 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 4 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 15; 47; 2 4 5 3 3 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no
 00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 5 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 5 3 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 5 3 3 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 3 4 2 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 4 3 4 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

(0; 15; 60; 2 5 4 4 3 3 3); 5th = 2; 4th = 2; FF = 1; Umin = no; Min = no; Max = no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 5 4 4 3 3 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 5 4 4 3 3 3 2; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 3 3 2 5; 5th = yes; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 3 2 5 4; 5th = no; 4th = yes; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 3 2 5 4 4; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 5 4 4 3; 5th = no; 4th = no; FF = no; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 5 4 4 3 3; 5th = yes; 4th = yes; FF = yes; Umin = no; min = no; Max = no; M347 = no

*Hyper-system No. 16; val.: 2 3 3 4 4 4 4***sys.: 15 ; 5ths: 30 ; 4ths: 30 ; FF: 18**

(0; 16; 1; 2 3 3 4 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 3 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

10 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 4 2 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 2; 2 3 4 3 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 4 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 2 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 3; 2 3 4 4 3 4 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 3 4 4 2; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 4 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

10 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 2 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 4; 2 3 4 4 4 3 4); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 4 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 3 4 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 4 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 3 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 5; 2 3 4 4 4 4 3); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 3 4 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 4 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 4 3 2 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 4 3 2 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 3 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 6; 2 4 3 3 4 4 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 3 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 3 4 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 3 2 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 13; 2 4 4 4 3 3 4); 5th=4; 4th=4; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

11 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 4 3 3 4 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 3 4 2 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 4 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 2 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 2 4 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 14; 2 4 4 4 3 4 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 4 3 4 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 3 4 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 3 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 3 2 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 16; 15; 2 4 4 4 4 3 3); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 2 4 4 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 2; value: 4 4 4 4 3 3 2; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 4 4 3 3 2 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 3 2 4 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 10 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 3 2 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 3 2 4 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
 00 sub-system N° 7; value: 3 2 4 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

Hyper-system No. 17; val.: 3 3 3 3 3 6

sys.: 1 ; 5ths: 0 ; 4ths0 ; FF 0

(0; 17; 1; 3 3 3 3 3 6); 5th=0; 4th=0; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 3 6; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 6 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 6 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 6 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 6 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 6 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 6 3 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 18 ; val.: 3 3 3 3 3 4 5***sys.: 6 ; 5ths: 12 ; 4ths: 12 ; FF 0**

(0; 18; 1; 3 3 3 3 3 4 5); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 3 4 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 4 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 4 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 5 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 5 3 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 3 3 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 18; 2; 3 3 3 3 3 5 4); 5th=1; 4th=1; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 3 5 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 3 5 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 3 5 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 5 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 5 4 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 5 4 3 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 18; 3; 3 3 3 3 4 3 5); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 4 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 5 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 3 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 3 3 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 18; 4; 3 3 3 3 5 3 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 5 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 5 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 5 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 5 3 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 5 3 4 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 3 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 18; 5; 3 3 3 4 3 3 5); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 4 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 3 5 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 5 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 5 3 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 5 3 3 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 18; 6; 3 3 3 5 3 3 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=0; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 5 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 5 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 5 3 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 5 3 3 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 3 4 3 3 3 5; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 3 3 3 5 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 5 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

*Hyper-system No. 19; val.: 3 3 3 3 4 4 4***sys.: 5 ; 5ths: 18 ; 4ths: 18 ; FF 9**

(0; 19; 1; 3 3 3 3 4 4 4); 5th=2; 4th=2; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 3 4 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 3 4 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 3 4 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 4 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 4 4 3 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 3 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

10 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 19; 2; 3 3 3 4 3 4 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 4 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 3 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 3 4 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 3 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 19; 3; 3 3 3 4 4 3 4); 5th=3; 4th=3; FF=1; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

00 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 3 4 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 3 4 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 3; value: 3 4 4 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 4 4 3 4 3 3 3; 5th=no; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 3 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 3 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 19; 4; 3 3 4 3 3 4 4); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

11 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 4 3 3 4 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 3 4 4 3; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 3 4 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 3 4 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 5; value: 3 4 4 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 6; value: 4 4 3 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

(0; 19; 5; 3 3 4 3 4 3 4); 5th=5; 4th=5; FF=3; Umin=no; Min=no; Max=no

11 sub-system N° 1; value: 3 3 4 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 2; value: 3 4 3 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 3; value: 4 3 4 3 4 3 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 4; value: 3 4 3 4 3 3 4; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 5; value: 4 3 4 3 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=no; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

00 sub-system N° 6; value: 3 4 3 3 4 3 4; 5th=no; 4th=yes; FF=no; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no

11 sub-system N° 7; value: 4 3 3 4 3 4 3; 5th=yes; 4th=yes; FF=yes; Umin=no; min=no; Max=no; M347=no
